

Benign Cystic Peritoneal Mesothelioma in a Young Woman as a Cause of Abdominal Pain: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Benign cystic mesothelioma (BCM) is a reactive proliferation of mesothelial cells in the peritoneum resulting from peritoneal injury. Also known as cystic mesothelioma of the peritoneum, it is characterized by the formation of multiple multilocular cysts that can develop into large intra-abdominal masses. Its pathogenesis remains controversial and has been associated with factors such as abdominal surgeries, trauma, and endometriosis, being more common in women of reproductive age. In Mexico, there are no extensive population-based studies determining its prevalence. Cases are usually diagnosed incidentally and may present with symptoms such as abdominal pain and intestinal obstruction. We present the case of a 25-year-old female patient with a history of inguinal hernia repair who consulted for abdominal pain and distension. A transvaginal ultrasound revealed free fluid and a 33×23 mm cyst. Laparoscopy revealed multiple vesicular lesions on the peritoneum, and cyst removal confirmed the diagnosis of BCM. The patient had a favorable postoperative course with complete symptom resolution. BCM is an uncommon neoplasm with a high recurrence rate. Definitive diagnosis is made through histopathological analysis. Although surgical resection is the mainstay of treatment, other therapies have been explored. This case highlights the typical presentation of BCM and the good prognosis following resection. BCM is rare and primarily affects young women. A clear diagnosis requires histological investigation, and surgical resection is essential to eliminate symptoms and prevent recurrence. Long-term follow-up is necessary due to the uncertainty regarding its etiology and the possibility of recurrence.

KEYWORDS: Benign cystic mesothelioma, Peritoneum, Surgical resection, Histopathological analysis, Recurrence, Laparoscopy, Abdominal surgery, case report.

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INTRODUCTION

Benign cystic mesothelioma [BCM] is a reactive proliferation of mesothelial cells of the peritoneum, considered a non-neoplastic entity that develops as a response to peritoneal injury [1]. It has also been referred to as multilocular peritoneal inclusion cysts, cystic mesothelioma of the peritoneum, and benign cystic mesothelioma, highlighting the ongoing lack of consensus regarding its etiology and biological behavior [2].

This condition is characterized by the formation of multiple thin-walled multilocular cysts, which frequently give rise to large intra-abdominal masses [3].

The pathogenesis of BCM remains controversial; among the predisposing factors are a history of abdominal or pelvic surgery, trauma, pelvic inflammatory disease, and endometriosis, among others [1].

Debate persists as to whether the disease process is predominantly reactive or neoplastic; however, the fact that the vast majority of affected individuals are women of reproductive age suggests a potential role of female sex hormones in its pathogenesis [3]. Unlike the malignant variety, BCM is not associated with asbestos exposure [4].

To date, fewer than 200 cases have been documented worldwide, accounting for approximately 3–5% of all peritoneal mesotheliomas. This condition is most frequently described in women of reproductive age, with an estimated female-to-male ratio of 4–5:1 [2]. No large-scale population-based studies are available in Mexico to accurately determine the prevalence of BCM. Most cases are diagnosed incidentally by imaging studies or during laparotomy performed for other indications. In other instances, the clinical presentation depends on the size and location of the lesion. Large cystic masses may be associated with abdominal pain, distension, intestinal obstruction, nausea, vomiting, weight loss, and/or alterations in bowel habits [4]. On physical examination, abdominal pain or distension may be noted, as well as a palpable abdominal or pelvic mass [2].

CASE REPORT

A 25-year-old female patient, Mexican, height 1.68 m, weight 56 kg, with no associated comorbidities, allergies or tobacco use, who reported only occasional alcohol consumption. Her surgical history included an inguinal hernia repair performed at five years of age. Gynecological and obstetric history included menarche at 14 years of age, onset of sexual activity at 20 years, no previous pregnancies, regular menstrual cycles every 21 days with bleeding lasting 8 days per cycle, and moderate to severe dysmenorrhea without habitual use of oral analgesics. Cervical cytology performed four years ago was negative for malignancy.

Our patient presented for medical evaluation due to abdominal pain and distension of one month duration, predominantly located in the right iliac fossa, with no other associated symptoms. Her vital signs were as follows: blood pressure 112/75 mmHg, heart rate 83 bpm, respiratory rate 18 rpm, and body temperature 36.3°C.

On examination, the patient was alert and oriented, with unremarkable cardiopulmonary findings. Abdominal examination revealed present peristalsis, tympany on percussion, and a soft, depressible abdomen on palpation, with no evidence of peritoneal irritation. Deep palpation elicited tenderness in the right iliac fossa, with a reported pain intensity of 6/10. No intra-abdominal masses were palpable. On vaginal speculum examination, the vagina and cervix appeared well epithelialized with no macroscopic abnormalities. Bimanual examination revealed a closed, punctate, mobile, and non-tender cervix.

A transvaginal ultrasound was performed, revealing a uterus in anteversion and anteflexion with regular borders measuring $7 \times 8 \times 4$ cm, an endometrial thickness of 9 mm, and ovaries of normal morphology and size, with multiple follicles. Free fluid was observed within the abdominal cavity, with septations in the posterior cul-de-sac, completely surrounding both ovaries, as well as in the perihepatic spaces and paracolic gutters (Figure 1–2). Tumor markers were requested and reported within normal limits.

Figure 1. Uterus in anteversion and anteflexion with regular borders measuring $7 \times 8 \times 4$ cm.

Figure 2. Endometrium measuring 9 mm in thickness.

On transvaginal ultrasound, cystic structures with anechoic content, regular borders, and thin walls were identified, measuring approximately 33 × 23 mm (Figures 3–4). No

ultrasonographic features suggestive of malignancy were observed.

Figure 3. Cystic lesion with anechoic content, regular borders, and thin wall, measuring approximately 33 × 23 mm.

Figure 4. Cystic images with anechoic content in the posterior sac, surrounding both ovaries.

A diagnostic laparoscopy was performed. During the procedure, vesicular lesions resembling "grape clusters" were

observed in the pouch of Douglas and the omentum (Figures 5–6). Multiple cysts of varying sizes were identified on the

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vesical peritoneum. Adhesiolysis was carried out with removal of visible cysts and peritoneal lavage, without intraoperative complications (Figure 7).

Figure 5. Vesicular lesions resembling “grape clusters” in the pouch of Douglas and omentum.

Figure 6. Pelvic view by laparoscopy showing a multiloculated cyst with whitish content of gelatinous or mucinous appearance, located in the adnexal or pelvic peritoneal region.

Figure 7. Presence of free serous fluid in the pelvic cavity with fine adhesions.

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The surgical specimen obtained was sent for histopathological analysis, which reported cysts with benign features, their walls lined by bland, flattened mesothelial cells. A focus of squamous metaplasia of the mesothelial

lining was also identified. The cysts were separated by fibrous septa, some of which were hyalinized, with patchy chronic inflammation. The final diagnosis was benign multicystic mesothelioma [Figure 8].

Figure 8. Histological sections obtained from the pathological specimen.

The patient was discharged in stable condition 24 hours after the laparoscopic procedure, without the need for major analgesia and with no evidence of immediate postoperative complications. During the first seven days postoperatively, she was followed up in an outpatient setting with monitoring for signs of infection, bleeding, abdominal pain, and bowel function, with no abnormal findings. Healing of the laparoscopic port sites was satisfactory, with no signs of inflammation.

At 4 and 12 weeks after discharge, clinical evaluations were performed, including gynecological physical examination and transvaginal ultrasound, with no evidence of fluid collections, cystic recurrence, or adnexal abnormalities. The patient reported complete resolution of preoperative symptoms, including intermittent pelvic pain and abdominal distension.

Annual follow-up was carried out through gynecological consultation and transvaginal ultrasound, as well as occasional abdominal ultrasound to assess the peritoneal cavity. At 6, 12, and 24 months postoperatively, no recurrence of cystic mesothelioma or development of new peritoneal lesions was identified. The patient remains asymptomatic, with preserved menstrual function and no signs of symptomatic adhesions.

Ongoing clinical surveillance is recommended given the rarity of benign cystic mesothelioma. Annual ultrasound and semiannual gynecological evaluations were advised for at least five years following the surgical intervention.

DISCUSSION

Benign cystic mesothelioma [BCM] is a rare mesothelial neoplasm first described by Mennemeyer and Smith in 1979 [5]. It is characterized by the presence of multiple peritoneal cysts lined by benign mesothelial cells. Although its behavior is non-invasive, a high rate of local recurrence has been observed, making it an entity with uncertain clinical behavior and a challenging surgical management. The estimated incidence is approximately 1 per 1,000,000 and it accounts for roughly one-third to one-fifth of all mesotheliomas [6].

The etiology of BCM is thought to be secondary to an inflammatory reaction occurring in the peritoneal tissue of the abdominopelvic cavity [3]. Peritoneal adhesions secondary to previous surgical interventions may extend to the ovarian surface, potentially distorting its contour without penetrating the ovarian parenchyma. When these adhesions surround the ovary and fluid accumulates, complex cystic masses may form, which are referred to as peritoneal inclusion cysts [1].

The macroscopic appearance of these cysts is typical: multiple translucent cysts arranged in “grape-like clusters” [7]. One hypothesis proposes that chronic peritoneal inflammation triggers proliferation and migration of peripheral mesothelial cells along with associated connective tissue, resulting in these cysts [4].

In the present case, the patient had a history of inguinal hernia repair in childhood, which may have acted as a predisposing factor by generating chronic peritoneal irritation — a theory

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supported by some studies as a possible etiopathogenic mechanism of BCM.

However, the absence of prior surgery or inflammation in some reported cases, together with the high recurrence rate [50–60%], has led others to suggest that the etiology of the disease is likely neoplastic [2].

A significant hormonal influence has also been proposed, as the condition occurs more frequently in women of reproductive age and it has been demonstrated that cyst size may decrease after treatment with a gonadotropin-releasing hormone agonist or tamoxifen [8].

Clinical findings are non-specific; patients commonly present with abdominal pain, a palpable mass, and symptoms related to compression of abdominal organs. Symptomatology depends on the size and location of the tumor. Large lesions may cause abdominal pain, fullness, distension, intestinal obstruction, nausea, vomiting, weight loss, and/or changes in bowel habits [4].

In many cases, BCM is an incidental finding during imaging studies or surgical procedures [9]. Imaging studies [ultrasound and computed tomography] do not reliably differentiate these lesions from other cystic entities, and aspiration cytology is generally inconclusive for preoperative diagnosis. Moreover, no standardized imaging protocols exist [8].

Due to its rarity, there are no established sensitivity and specificity values for imaging studies in BCM. Definitive diagnosis requires histopathological analysis following biopsy or surgical resection [4].

Ultrasound is the most commonly used imaging technique for incidental detection of these lesions. Other imaging modalities, such as CT and MRI, can help confirm the diagnosis [1].

Computed tomography has high sensitivity [$>80\%$] for detecting cystic masses and a specificity of approximately 50–60%, but it has limitations in differentiating BCM from other malignant or inflammatory cystic lesions [10].

Magnetic resonance imaging has a high sensitivity [80–90%] for characterizing cystic lesions, with moderate specificity [60–70%]. MRI provides better characterization of septa, content, and enhancement patterns, improving differentiation between benign and malignant lesions compared to CT [10].

The macroscopic and microscopic appearance in this case is consistent with what has been described in the literature: multiple cystic lesions of varying sizes, lined by mesothelial cells and separated by thin septa of loose connective tissue with vascular stroma, acute and chronic inflammatory infiltrates, and areas of squamous metaplasia [3].

By immunohistochemistry, mesothelial cells typically express calretinin and, in some cases, estrogen and progesterone receptors [11]. However, detection of estrogen or progesterone receptors is uncommon [3].

The mesothelial nature is demonstrated by immunoreactivity of tumor cells for HBME-1, which is frequently positive in mesothelial tumors, and negativity for vascular markers — an

important finding for the differential diagnosis with vascular tumors such as cystic lymphangioma [11].

While surgical excision of the cysts remains the mainstay of treatment, alternative therapies have been attempted, including sclerotherapy with tetracycline, continuous hyperthermic peritoneal perfusion with cisplatin, and peritonectomy with intraperitoneal chemotherapy [3]. The interval between prior surgery and the development of these cysts ranges from 6 months to 20 years [2].

Some reports have described the use of the gonadotropin-releasing hormone agonist leuprolide and the anti-estrogenic agent tamoxifen in a single patient with recurrent BCM, suggesting that inducing a hypoestrogenic state may be therapeutically beneficial in selected cases. The authors reported a reduction in cyst volume and maintenance of cyst size with symptomatic relief while the patient was receiving therapy [3].

This condition has a high recurrence rate, and although definitive treatment is cyst excision, the use of sclerosing agents such as tetracycline or cisplatin, as well as peritonectomy with chemotherapy, remains controversial but has shown efficacy [12].

The detection of estrogen and progesterone receptors on the tumor surface appears to be key; thus, future treatment may rely on determining the hormonal expression profile and administering the appropriate blocking agent for each case [12].

Postoperative follow-up includes clinical evaluation and imaging studies; however, there are currently no established follow-up guidelines for this condition [4].

This case illustrates a typical presentation of BCM in a young patient, with suggestive clinical and imaging findings confirmed by histology. Complete resection without evidence of early recurrence supports a favorable prognosis in cases managed surgically.

CONCLUSION

Benign cystic peritoneal mesothelioma is a rare condition that primarily affects young women. A definitive diagnosis can only be established through histological examination, as clinical and imaging findings are typically non-specific. This case report highlights the importance of performing thorough surgical resection as the mainstay of treatment to alleviate symptoms and prevent short- and medium-term recurrence. Although the prognosis following surgery is generally favorable, the fact that the underlying cause remains uncertain — whether reactive or neoplastic — and the potential for recurrence underscore the need for long-term clinical and ultrasonographic follow-up to ensure optimal management of this uncommon entity.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

In this case report, the identifying information has been removed from all patient-related data.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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